

The Amazon: A Potential Tipping Point in The Earth's Climate System

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What is the concern?

The Amazon rainforest system is under extreme pressure, with 17%–20% of the forested area cleared over the past 50 years (1), the majority of which was converted into agricultural land (2). Of the remaining forest, 38% is currently considered degraded and at risk of disappearing (3).

The combination of stressors originating both from climate change and deforestation could trigger a partial or total dieback of the Amazon rainforest in the near future, resulting in a critical transition from tropical forest to savanna.

How close is the Amazon rainforest to irreversible change?

An Amazon forest tipping point would likely be an irreversible change because it is estimated that it would take over 100 years to regrow to its previous state and ecosystem function (4). Climate model simulations

suggest that the rainforest could collapse into a savanna-like state in a wide range of temperatures, from 2°C to 6°C global warming above the pre-industrial levels, with the most likely range between 3°C and 4°C (5, 6).

With additional deforestation, the Amazon ecosystem will be more susceptible to climate change and at risk of transitioning at lower global warming levels.

**The Amazon:
A biodiversity
hotspot**

10%
of the
planet's
species

15% of the
world's river
discharge
into oceans

Affects global and
regional rainfall
through
evapotranspiration

Critical element of
the world's climate
system as a major
carbon sink

What would the consequences be?

An Amazon rainforest collapse would have catastrophic consequences for the 47 million people living in the Legal Amazon, who depend on the ecosystem services of the forest. It would severely impact the food and water security of the population of Brazil, due to a reduction in the moisture recycling and cooling effect of the forest (7). Globally, if the Amazon were to switch from being a sink to a source of CO₂, impacts would be experienced across the world due to the enhancement of human-induced climate change.

In Brazil, such a transition would lead to major food and water insecurities (8), particularly affecting food producing areas in south eastern regions of the country. A shift in the ecosystem function of the forest would also lead to biodiversity loss, the spread of infectious diseases (1, 9), and increased propagation of arboviruses (10). If they were to happen, these impacts are expected to drive mass migration and generate far-reaching political instability (11).

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What are the factors that still need to be investigated?

The previous generation of climate models indicated no regional Amazon rainforest diebacks until the end of the century (12). Today, more comprehensive earth system models are available that incorporate vegetation interactions with the climate, biome shifts, land use change and new processes such as forest fires (13). New findings from Brazilian-led field experiments in the Amazon, such as AmazonFACE, LBA and ATTO (a, b, c) are enabling future developments on even more complex processes, such as

ecosystem demography and phosphorus limitation. Depending on the global warming and deforestation scenario, simulations using these newer models indicate that the Amazon rainforest could be vulnerable to partial or large-scale collapse (6, 14) at lower warming levels than previously thought. More detailed experiments with the latest generation of climate models are needed to constrain the global warming thresholds and conditions beyond which the Amazon rainforest system could undergo a tipping point.

The region is also affected by major climate patterns such as El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) (15). The warm phase El Niño is associated with widespread drought and high temperatures in the Amazon, leading to droughts and an increase in forest fires, while the cold phase, La Niña, with enhanced precipitation and flooding in parts of the forest (16, 17, 18). Changes in the strength and frequency of El Niño and La Niña events could put an additional pressure on the Amazon and more research is needed to understand this.

How will the TipESM project help address this issue?

The TipESM project will produce a range of new climate simulations specially tailored to investigate the sensitivity of the Amazon rainforest to global warming. They will test the long-term response of the Amazon rainforest to a warming of 0.2°C per decade, response to climate

stabilization at 2°C and 4°C above the pre-industrial levels, and a subsequent return to the pre-industrial levels. These simulations will also allow us to study how the major climate patterns, including the ENSO cycle, can change with global warming and how such changes

would affect the Amazon. Ongoing TipESM analyses suggest that in the future, extreme heat episodes linked to El Niño will have a major negative impact on the state of the forest, potentially triggering destabilizing droughts and forest fires (19).

What is TipESM?

TipESM is a research project aimed at delivering a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on

ecosystems and society, as well early warning indicators of tipping points and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

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Website: <https://tipesm.eu>

(a) <https://amazonface.unicamp.br>

(b) <http://www.igbp.net/>

(c) <https://www.attoproject.org/>

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Project partners and associated partners

- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (and their affiliated entities)
- The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
- University of Bergen
- The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
- Barcelona Institute for Global Health
- University of Leeds
- Met Office UK
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